

EVALUATING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INDUSTRIAL DISPUTE MECHANISM PROCESS IN LEADING PUBLIC SECTOR UNDERTAKING

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Abstract

This study evaluates the effectiveness of industrial dispute mechanisms process at a leading public sector undertaking (PSU) in Chennai, focusing on its South Regional Office which handles disputes across four South Indian states. The research aims to assess the existing dispute resolution procedures and identify areas for improvement to enhance productivity, working conditions, and employee satisfaction. The study uses a descriptive design to analyse perceptions of the industrial dispute process, challenges in dispute management, and legal compliance. Data was collected from 31 employees of the PSU through questionnaires, with a focus on permanent employees, excluding trainees and contract workers. The findings indicate that a significant portion of respondents have a low perception on the effectiveness of the dispute resolution process, with mediocre knowledge of legal compliance. Statistical analysis reveals no significant association between years of experience and compliance with labour laws. However, there is a notable difference between genders regarding the effectiveness of dispute resolution processes and outcomes. The study suggests the PSU to implement regular training programs on labour laws and conflict resolution, establish a computerized grievance redressal system, and promote open communication channels. The IR team is advised to conduct frequent training, establish a mediation panel, and regularly survey employee satisfaction to enhance policies and maintain a productive workplace.

Keywords: Industrial disputes, public sector undertaking, dispute resolution, workplace harmony, employee satisfaction, labour law compliance, grievance redressal, industrial relations.

Introduction

The largest oil and gas firm in India, leading public sector undertaking, provides essential services to the country's energy sector and makes a substantial contribution to its economic expansion. Being a public sector organization, leading public sector undertaking is bound by a number of labour laws and rules designed to effectively settle workplace conflicts. Disagreements can nevertheless affect employee satisfaction and organizational productivity in spite of these safeguards. Studying the efficacy of industrial conflict systems is made

possible by the South Regional Office of leading public sector undertaking, which is situated in Chennai and handles disputes in all four South Indian states.

Like many other industries, the oil and gas sector have issues with working conditions, employment terms, and job circumstances, all of which can result in labour conflicts. These conflicts frequently entail arguments inside the workforce or between employers and employees. In order to maintain a positive work atmosphere and guarantee organizational effectiveness, these conflicts must be handled effectively. The purpose of the study is to assess how well leading public sector undertaking's present dispute resolution procedure works and pinpoint areas that could be improved by enhancing productivity and working conditions. The background of the study is also influenced by the larger Indian industrial relations context. While India's labour laws and regulations offer a framework for settling workplace conflicts, the efficiency of these processes can fluctuate depending on the sector and company. This study adds to a larger understanding of industrial dispute resolution in India's public sector undertakings by looking at the particular situation of leading public sector undertaking. Human resource managers, industrial relations officers, and researchers looking to improve dispute resolution procedures in comparable settings may find value in the study's conclusions and suggestions.

Methodology:

Aim:

To evaluate the effectiveness of industrial dispute mechanism process at leading public sector undertaking.

Hypotheses:

1. **H0:** There is no significant association among the years of experience of the respondents and compliance with all labour laws and regulations.
2. **H1:** There is a significant difference between the gender of the respondents and overall industrial dispute mechanism process.
3. **H0:** There is no significant difference between the designation of the respondents and overall industrial dispute mechanism process.

Research design:

The researcher adopted descriptive design in describing the levels and dimensions of Industrial Disputes and their mechanism to handle conflicts in an organization to maintain a harmonious relationship Ans also increasing the productivity. This design brings out important factors such

as perception of industrial dispute process, challenges in dispute management and legal compliance in a dispute process. This has given a chance to evaluate whether the dispute process is adequate or need some improvement and also help to find out the advance method to resolve the conflicts in the leading public sector undertaking.

Universe & Sampling:

The universe of the study consists of 235 employees working in a leading public sector undertaking, Chennai. The simple random sampling technique using the lottery method was used and 15% of the total was taken for the study. This resulted in 35 employees being selected respectively. Since, pre testing was done with 4 respondents. They were excluded from the study. This resulted in a total sample size of 31 respondents being finalizing and selecting for the study.

Tools for Data Collection:

Primary data was gathered with the help of questionnaires that had closed-ended and open-ended questions, and the respondents of the employees were measured through a Likert scale to check the effectiveness of industrial dispute process. Secondary data was gathered from books, journals, research papers, and authentic websites to give background information on the effectiveness of industrial dispute mechanism.

Results and Discussion:

Table 1

Distribution of Respondents based on overall industrial dispute mechanism process at leading public sector undertaking

Industrial Dispute Mechanism	Low	Percentage (%)	High	Percentage (%)
Perception on effectiveness of Dispute Resolution Process	16	51.6	15	48.4
Effectiveness of the process and outcomes	20	64.5	11	35.5
Legal compliance	17	54.8	14	45.2
Overall Industrial dispute mechanism process	14	45.2	17	54.8

Considering the provided table 1, majority of respondents (64.5%) have low levels of process and outcome frequencies in regular disputes. More than half (54.8%) of the employees have mediocre knowledge in legal compliance with the dispute resolution process. more than half (51.6%) of the respondents have a low level of perception on dispute resolution process. More than two fifth (45.2%) of the respondents have low level of industrial dispute mechanism process. More than half (54.8%) of the respondents are having high level in overall industrial dispute mechanism. It's also shows that less than half (48.4%) of the respondents have high level of perception on dispute resolution process. More than two fifth (45.2%) of the employees have renowned knowledge in legal compliance with industrial dispute process. More than one-third (35.5%) have high levels of knowledge on the process and outcome frequencies.

Table 2

Pearson Chi- square among Compliance with all relevant labour laws and regulations as per the years of experience of the respondents

Years of experience of the respondents		Compliance with all relevant labour laws and regulations			Total
		Not confident	Neutral	Confident	
Less than 5 Years	Count	0	5	0	5
	Row	0.0%	17.2%	0.0%	16.1%
	Column	0.0%	16.1%	0.0%	16.1%
5 – 10 Years	Count	0	8	1	9
	Row	0.0%	27.6%	100.0%	29.0%
	Column	0.0%	25.8%	3.2%	29.0%
11 – 15 Years	Count	1	10	0	11
	Row	100.0%	34.5%	0.0%	35.5%
	Column	3.2%	32.3%	0.0%	35.5%
More than 15 Years	Count	0	6	0	6
	Row	0.0%	20.7%	0.0%	19.4%
	Column	0.0%	19.4%	0.0%	19.4%
Total	Count	1	29	1	31
	Row	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	Column	3.2%	93.5%	3.2%	100.0%

Chi-Square Test: Value: 4.341, DF: 6, P= .631

The above table shows that one fifth (16.1%) of the respondents comes under less than 5 years of experience, more than two forth (29%) of the respondents are fall under 5 – 10 years of experience, more than one third (35.5%) of the respondents comes under 11 – 15 years of experience and less than one fifth (19.4%) of the respondents have above 15 years of experience. The result of this test is not significant that means there is no significant association among the years of experience of the respondents and compliance with all labour laws and regulations.

H0: There is no significant association among the years of experience of the respondents and compliance with all labour laws and regulations.

H1: There is no significant association among the years of experience of the respondents and compliance with all labour laws and regulations.

Result: The test was applied to comparing two variables. Years of experience of the respondents and the Compliance with all relevant labour laws and regulations. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected.

Table 3

't'-Test based on gender of the respondents and overall industrial dispute mechanism process

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Df	Statistical Inference
Perception of the dispute resolution process						
Male	19	29.32	2.583	.593	29	't'=0.247 P>0.05 Not Significant
Female	12	30.75	4.202	1.213	16.309	
Frequency of the process and outcomes						
Male	19	24.32	2.029	.465	29	't'=0.012 P<0.05 Significant
Female	12	22.00	2.763	.798	18.459	
Overall Effectiveness of industrial dispute mechanism process						
Male	19	72.84	3.270	.750	29	't'=0.344 P>0.05 Not significant
Female	12	71.42	4.999	1.443	16.992	

The table shows that there is no significant difference between the gender of the respondents in terms of their overall industrial dispute mechanism. There is a significant difference between gender of the respondents and the frequency of the process and outcomes. There is no significant difference between gender of the respondents and the overall effectiveness of industrial dispute mechanism process.

H0: There is no significant difference between gender of the respondents and overall industrial dispute mechanism process.

H1: There is a significant difference between the gender of the respondents and overall industrial dispute mechanism process.

Results: The t-test was employed to assess how respondents' genders affected their opinions of the leading public sector undertaking industrial dispute resolution process. It was discovered that respondents' overall opinions of the industrial dispute mechanism process did not significantly differ between males and females. The null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 4

't'-Test based on designation and overall effectiveness of industrial dispute mechanism process

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Df	Statistical Inference
Perception of the dispute resolution process						
Below manager	25	30.32	2.940	.588	29	't'=0.125 P>0.05 Not Significant
Above manager	6	28.00	4.382	1.789	6.124	
Frequency of the process and outcomes						
Below manager	25	23.24	2.554	.511	29	't'=0.436 P>0.05 Not Significant
Above manager	6	24.17	2.714	1.108	7.283	
Overall Effectiveness of industrial dispute mechanism process						
Below manager	25	72.64	3.315	.663	29	't'=0.330 P>0.05 Not significant
Above manager	6	70.83	6.369	2.600	5.666	

The table shows that there is no significant relationship with regard to the designation and the perception of the dispute resolution process. There is no significant relationship with regard to the designation of the respondents and frequency of the process and outcomes. There is no significant difference with regard to the designation of the respondents in terms of their overall dispute mechanism.

H0: There is no significant difference between the designation of the respondents and overall industrial dispute mechanism process.

H1: There is a significant difference between the designation of the respondents and overall industrial dispute mechanism process.

Results: Since there is no significant difference in the overall effectiveness of the industrial dispute mechanism process between employees of different designations, the null hypothesis

is accepted. The t-test was used to assess the differences in perceptions of the process based on the designation of employees at leading public sector undertaking. Implement standardized dispute resolution training for all designations to maintain consistent understanding about industrial relations to avoid disputes.

Suggestions:

The study should think about include more staff members in the research process in order to obtain a more thorough and clearer picture of labour issues. To get their real experiences and viewpoints on conflicts within the company, managers and staff may be surveyed or interviewed. Additionally, contrasting the approaches taken by top public sector initiatives to resolve labour disputes with those of comparable firms can highlight successful methods and approaches. Employees can be better prepared to handle conflicts with confidence by implementing focused labour law training programs, and an electronic dispute resolution system can expedite and improve efficiency.

Suggestions for the organisations:

The organization should concentrate on a number of important projects in order to improve the industrial dispute settlement procedure. Initially, it is imperative to provide thorough training programs focused on legal compliance and conflict resolution, since many respondents had low perceptions of the efficacy of the current procedure. Employees will get more knowledge and self-assurance in handling conflict as a result of this training. Establishing more transparent channels of communication is also essential to ensuring that staff members are at ease voicing concerns and offering input; frequent town hall meetings and anonymous feedback systems help promote an open culture. To find areas that require improvement, the business should also periodically evaluate the conflict resolution procedure. To do this, focus groups and employee satisfaction surveys should be used to collect qualitative information about the experiences of the employees.

Suggestions for the IR Department:

The Industrial Relations (IR) department should execute a number of important efforts to increase its effectiveness. Initially, the IR division ought to create customized training courses for various staff levels that emphasize legal observance, dispute resolution techniques, and efficient communication methods. Employees will have the skills they need to handle conflicts with confidence thanks to this focused training. Establishing mediation procedures in the IR division can also speed up settlements by resolving conflicts before they become official grievances, which will enhance employee relations. Conducting audits will guarantee that all

employees are aware of their rights and obligations; regular monitoring of compliance with labour laws and regulations is essential.

Suggestion for training and development department:

Enhancing the efficacy of organizational industrial dispute resolution procedures is mostly dependent on training and development. Organizations can provide their employees with the skills they need to handle conflicts by putting in place thorough training programs that emphasize communication, conflict resolution, and legal compliance... These programs ought to be customized for various staff levels, guaranteeing that management and employees are aware of their responsibilities in the dispute resolution procedure. Employees can also stay current on conflict management best practices and new trends by participating in continuous development programs, which can promote a culture of continuous learning.

Suggestions for quality research and design department:

In the field of industrial conflict resolution, future academics have a number of exciting directions to pursue. Investigating longitudinal trends is one important field that would entail monitoring shifts in opinions about conflict resolution procedures over time in order to learn more about the long-term efficacy of tactics that have been put into place. Furthermore, using qualitative research techniques like focus groups or interviews can offer more in-depth understandings of how employees deal with conflicts, leading to a more complex comprehension of the underlying problems. Examining cross-industry comparisons of industrial dispute processes could also be helpful to researchers, as it could reveal special difficulties and successful strategies that could be modified for projects in the public sector.

Conclusion:

The study on the efficiency of the Southern Regional Office of leading public sector undertaking's industrial dispute mechanism emphasizes how important structured dispute resolution procedures are to preserving employee happiness and workplace harmony. According to the findings, despite leading public sector undertaking's official conflict resolution procedure, employee opinions, resolution frequency, and understanding of legal compliance fluctuate depending on experience level and position. The statistical research shows that years of experience, gender, and designation have no discernible effects on the conflict resolution process's overall efficacy. However, in order to increase compliance and conflict management, there is need for development in legal training, grievance redressal efficiency, and communication. Establishing frequent training programs, enhancing feedback systems, and guaranteeing open communication between staff and management are all ways that leading public sector undertaking might fortify its industrial relations framework.

Grievances can also be handled more effectively by implementing technology-driven dispute tracking and resolution systems. To promote a more efficient and peaceful workplace, the study emphasizes the significance of ongoing assessment and improvement of industrial conflict procedures. In the end, leading public sector undertaking can contribute to a more stable and forward-thinking workplace by tackling these issues and improving organizational effectiveness, employee trust, and labour law compliance.

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